

A COMPARISON OF LINEAR AND NONLINEAR SCALE-SPACE FILTERS IN NOISE

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ABSTRACT

The properties of two scale-space systems are compared by examining their performance in noise. It is found that in Gaussian noise linear diffusion and a new type of filter called the area sieve have similar performance but in impulsive noise of random amplitude the area sieve is superior.

1 INTRODUCTION

The advantages of scale-space have been well reported [1, 2], and working systems that adopt a scale-space approach have started to appear in the literature [3, 4]. The fundamental requirement is that, at increasing scale, the number of extrema in the image should decrease so that, at large scales, the task of processing the image is reduced. Most reported scale-space processors are based on linear, or nonlinear, diffusion equations but these have problems. Linear diffusion systems smear the edges which means that large-scale segmentations do not coincide with small-scale ones. Non-linear diffusion systems overcome this, but are slow to compute and require a carefully chosen diffusion function. Neither is *scale-calibrated*: the scale parameter, s does not give the true size of the objects in an image smoothed to particular scale.

An alternative is to use a morphological scale-space preserving filter [5, 6, 7]. These filters are scale-calibrated since the scale parameter is associated with an integer number of pixels. Furthermore, they are often quick to compute [8, 9]. This paper discusses the performance of a new filter called a *sieve* that decomposes an image by area. The filter is characterised by examining its performance in noise and comparing it to that achieved by the linear diffusion system.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE PROCESSORS

Linear diffusion-based scale-space processors are well documented elsewhere [1]. In this paper the scale-space was generated using separable filters ($\gamma = 0$) where the

image at scale s is computed as

$$f^{(s)}(x, y) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} T(m; s) \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} T(n; s) f(x - m, y - n) \quad (1)$$

where $f(x, y)$ is the pixel value at position (x, y) and $f^{(s)}(x, y)$ is the pixel value after smoothing to scale s . $T(n; s)$ is the discrete approximation to the Gaussian kernel

$$T(n; s) = e^{-s} I_n(s) \quad (2)$$

and $I_n(s)$ is the modified Bessel function of the first kind. The scale-selection surface ([1] p. 323)

$$d = s^2 \left(f_{xx}^{(s)} + f_{yy}^{(s)} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

is used to locate the scale-space estimate.

The area-sieve is also documented elsewhere [10] but the basis of the algorithm is to consider an image as a graph $G = (V, E)$. The set of edges E describes the adjacency of the pixels (which are the vertices V). The algorithm proceeds by defining a region, $C_r(G, x)$ over the graph that encloses the pixel (vertex) x ,

$$C_r(G, x) = \{\xi \in C_r(G) | x \in \xi\} \quad (4)$$

where $C_r(G)$ is the set of connected subsets of G with r elements. Thus $C_r(G, x)$ is the set of connected subsets of r elements that contain x . For each integer $r \geq 1$ the operators $\psi_r, \gamma_r, \mathcal{M}^r, \mathcal{N}^r : \mathbf{Z}^V \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}^V$ are defined as

$$\psi_r f(x) = \max_{\xi \in C_r(G, x)} \min_{u \in \xi} f(u), \quad (5)$$

$$\gamma_r f(x) = \min_{\xi \in C_r(G, x)} \max_{u \in \xi} f(u), \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{M}^r = \gamma_r \psi_r, \quad \mathcal{N}^r = \psi_r \gamma_r. \quad (7)$$

$\mathcal{M}^r$ is a greyscale opening followed by a closing defined over a region of size r and $\mathcal{N}^r$ is a greyscale closing followed by an opening over the same region.

The types of sieve known as M - or N -sieve are formed by repeated operation of the $\mathcal{M}$ or $\mathcal{N}$ operators. An M -sieve of f is the sequence $(f^{(r)})_{r=1}^{\infty}$ given by

$$f^{(1)} = \mathcal{M}^1 f, \quad f^{(r+1)} = \mathcal{M}^{r+1} f^{(r)}, \quad r \geq 1 \quad (8)$$

Figure 1: The original image, f , has two unit-area extrema and one of area nine

The N -sieve is defined similarly. The output of an area sieve is usually taken to be the set of *granule functions*

$$d^{(r)} = f^{(r)} - f^{(r+1)} \quad \text{for each integer } r \geq 1 \quad (9)$$

These form the scale selection surface and non-zero connected regions within granule functions are called granules.. Each granule has sharp edges and, at a particular scale, all granules have the same area. In this sense the sieve is *scale calibrated*.

An example of the operation of the area sieve is shown in Figure 1 and 2. Figure 1 shows a twenty-five pixel image with one maximum in the centre and one minimum in the top left.

Figure 2: $f^{(2)}$ (top left), $d^{(1)}$ (top right), $f^{(10)}$ (bottom left), $d^{(9)}$ (bottom right)

The first application of the sieve yields $f^{(1)} = f$ and so is not shown. The top left of Figure 2 shows $f^{(2)}$ which is $f^{(1)}$ with all the extrema of unit area removed. The top right of Figure 2 shows $|d^{(1)}|$. There are granules

Figure 3: The woman's features appear at different scales

where there was a maximum and a minimum. The remaining feature has area of nine pixels so $f^{(2)} \dots f^{(9)}$ are identical and are not shown. The bottom left of Figure 2 shows $f^{(10)}$ in which central nine-pixel maximum has been removed and on the bottom right of Figure 2 is $|d^{(9)}|$ which shows the corresponding granule.

For the simple image shown in Figure 1 the sieve decomposition has only a few images but for a 100 by 100 pixel image there are 10^4 possible scale-space filtered images. So, for the purposes of display and for approximate scale determination, the outputs over a range of scales are summed to form a *channel*. Figure 3 shows the channels from an image of person. Features of different sizes appear in different spatial channels and those that had sharp edges retain them. The nostrils, eyes and mouth are localised in scale and space and such a decomposition is a good starting point for an accurate segmentation.

3 RESULTS

Real images are corrupted by noise and contain distortions such as 'glint'. In an attempt to simulate some of these effects the images were corrupted with either Gaussian or impulsive noise. The target image consisted of a disc or square of amplitude 144 in the centre of a 100 by 100 pixel image with background 112. To this, was added either uncorrelated Gaussian noise ($\mu = 0, \sigma = 24$), or alternatively, pixels were replaced with a random value in the range $(-6, 6)$ with a probability of 0.2. The resulting image was clipped into the range $(0, 255)$. The impulsive noise was chosen to give spikes of similar amplitude and occurrence probability to the glints observed in real images. Figure 4 shows

Figure 4: Examples of noise-corrupted images: Gaussian noise (top) and Impulsive noise (bottom)

examples of the target images.

For both systems an iterative search was conducted over all scales to find the maximum. Scattergrams of results from 150 trials of the image corrupted by Gaussian noise for the two systems are shown in Figure 5. Each graph shows the estimates as circular markers with their co-ordinates being the estimates of x , y and s . The light-grey dots are the projection of the points in three-space onto each pair of axes. The linear scale-space processor has been scale-calibrated by normalising the mean of the cluster to equal the true area of the disc.

In the linear scale-space processor the peak was the maximum value of the normalised Hessian (3). To improve the precision of the position estimates a quadratic surface was least-squares fitted to the peak and its four-connected neighbours. The position of this peak gave the (x, y) position estimate. Since the area sieve operates by “slicing off” the peaks and troughs, at a particular scale, the extrema are large and flat. So, to obtain the position of the disc, the centroid of all the pixels that had the value as the maximum at a particular scale was computed.

Examining Figure 5 shows that, in Gaussian noise, the two systems have comparable performance. Studies with the equivalent one-dimensional filters [7] showed that the linear diffusion system was more sensitive to Gaussian noise than the sieve. In two-dimensions this is not the case, probably because the scale-selection surface (3) in two-dimensions performs more spatial averaging.

For impulsive noise, Figure 6, the systems have very different behaviours. The sieve is hardly affected. This

Figure 5: Estimates with Gaussian noise, disc target. Diffusion is on top, Sieve at the bottom

is an important property since in real vision systems impulses, glint and occlusion are commonplace.

The results are summarised in Table 1 which gives the sample standard deviations of the scale and position estimates.

		Gaussian noise		Impulsive noise	
		Diffusion	Sieve	Diffusion	Sieve
Disc	x	0.643	0.280	0.925	0.0425
	y	0.629	0.243	0.790	0.0416
	s	32.4	55.0	57.9	3.91
Square	x	0.738	0.280	1.03	0.0457
	y	0.646	0.288	0.864	0.0460
	s	37.7	50.2	139.0	4.216

Table 1: Standard deviations of the estimates of x , y and s

4 DISCUSSION

The performance of the sieve in impulsive noise is unsurprising since it is known that, in one dimension, $\mathcal{M}$ and $\mathcal{N}$ filters behave similarly to median filters which have

Figure 6: Estimates with Impulsive noise, disc target. Diffusion is on top, Sieve at the bottom

good performance in impulsive noise. The sieve retains its performance in Gaussian noise probably because the cascaded operation described in (8) means that the output at large scales has a large support providing spatial averaging.

Since the sieve operates on area it is not affected by the geometry of the objects in the image. For example, if these estimation experiments are repeated with a rectangular target then the diffusion processor behaves poorly unless the image is simplified using an anisotropic diffusion system in which the anisotropy matches the aspect ratio of the rectangle.

References

- [1] Tony Lindeberg. *Scale-space theory in computer vision*. Kluwer Academic, Dordrecht, Netherlands, 1994.
- [2] Bart M. ter Harr Romeny, editor. *Geometry-driven diffusion in Computer vision*. Kluwer Academic, Dordrecht, Netherlands, 1994. ISBN 0-7923-3087-0.

- [3] A. Lanitis, C.J.Taylor, and T.F.Cootes. A unified approach to coding and interpreting face images. In *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 368–373, 1995.
- [4] Thomas Koller, G.Grieg, Gabor Szekely, and Daniel Dettwiler. Multiscale detection of curvilinear structures in 2d and 3d image data. In *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 864–869, 1995.
- [5] Luc Vincent. Grayscale are openings and closings, their efficient implementation and applications. In Jean Serra and Phillipe Salembier, editors, *Proceedings of the international workshop on mathematical morphology and its applications to signal processing*, pages 22–27, May 1993.
- [6] R. van den Boomgaard and A. Smeulders. The morphological structure of images: the differential equations of morphological scale-space. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 16(11):1101–1113, November 1994.
- [7] J. Andrew Bangham, Paul Ling, and Richard Harvey. Scale-space from nonlinear filters. In *Proceedings of the First International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 163–168, 1995.
- [8] Luc Vincent. Morphological grayscale reconstruction in image analysis: applications and efficient algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, 2(2):176–201, April 1993.
- [9] J. A. Bangham, S. J. Impey, and F. W. D. Woodhams. A fast 1d sieve transform for multiscale signal decomposition. In *EUSIPCO*, 1994.
- [10] J. Andrew Bangham, Richard Harvey, Paul D. Ling, and Richard V. Aldridge. Nonlinear scale-space from n -dimensional sieves. In *Computer Vision – ECCV’ 96*, pages 189–198, 1996.